

Deliverable D6

Title

Guideline describing the concept of UniTerm (Unified user interface) and how to establish secure communication interfaces in legal metrology

EMPIR Grant Agreement number

17IND02

Project short name

SmartCom

Leading partner

PTB (Wiebke Heeren)

Due date

2021-04-30

Submission date

2021-11-09

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5704676

